

From Text to Practice: New Testament Ethics on Homosexuality in the African Context

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Abstract

The Bible particularly the New Testament (NT) is the core text for Christians used as a reference point for faith, teachings and morality. However, Christian theologians, in some cases informed by their denominational and theological leanings, are grappling with various challenges posed by the diverse interpretations of the NT regarding ethical decisions, particularly within the diversity of the present African contexts. The key concern in this paper is to examine how the NT could be a resource for ethics and or morality within the African setup. This calls for a relevant hermeneutical approach that enables moving from text (NT) in its context to practice in the African situation. It necessitates a comprehensive examination of prevailing approaches to NT ethics particularly with the aim of responding to the challenge of homosexuality. This paper is guided by two primary objectives: first, to assess scholarly perspectives on NT ethics, and second, to examine the question of homosexuality from a Christian point of view within the African situation. Through these objectives, the paper seeks to contribute to the ongoing dialogue on reconciling and using scriptural teaching on ethical understanding in the African context. The paper employs relevant hermeneutics to examine pertinent NT passages within the African context, particularly focusing on the discourse surrounding homosexuality. It involves an assessment of various ethical models advanced by NT scholars with the aim of showing their relevance to the issue of homosexuality and by extension matters related to sexuality within the African context. The discussion reveals diverse scholarly views on NT ethics, ranging from literalist interpretations to contextual understandings informed by cultural and historical insights. Furthermore, it is noted that majority of African communities disapprove the practice of homosexuality. The paper concludes by underscoring the importance of engaging with NT text first with its context to get its original meaning in order to apply it within the African context. While acknowledging the challenges of reconciling scripture with traditional African cultural understanding, it proposes the need for continued thoughtful dialogue touching on the relevant ethical challenges. The paper recommends the development of contextualized theological resources and pastoral practices that are sensitive to the realities and experiences related to homosexuality in Africa.

Key words: homosexuality, New Testament Ethics, morality

Introduction

Ethics encompasses the conscientious examination of moral behaviors and character. According to Kunhiyop (2008, p.4), the interconnection of ethics and morality is exemplified through the delineation that 'ethics' encapsulates the definitions, principles, and incentives driving conduct and character. Scholars have proposed diverse ethical frameworks, often conflicting, to address the contemporary ethical perspectives and issues. These range from antinomianism, situationism, and generalism, to unqualified absolutism, conflicting absolutism, and graded absolutism, among others (Geisler, 2010).

Within this subject of ethical concerns, numerous contentious issues persist, including abortion, infanticide, euthanasia, biomedical questions, capital punishment, war, civil disobedience, ecology, animal rights, marriage and divorce, sexual mores, and homosexuality. Christianity across the globe over time has exhibited different and shifting perspectives on these issues guided by several factors for instance prevailing philosophies and other social and cultural leanings. Wilkens (2017) identifies various dynamics that inform how Christians arrive at the understanding of ethics or moral law. They include theological traditions, the awareness of the source of the moral knowledge, interpretation regarding the role of individual volitional capacity, and the place of human reason in decision-making (Wilkens, 2017, pp.2-3). Christian ethicists, historically and presently could be broadly grouped, though some overlap, under four categories or theories based on their views. The four are divine command theory, virtue ethics, natural law and prophetic ethics (Wilkens, 2017). This paper attempts to show the importance of the NT and the need to move from scripture to practice in the African context.

In recent years, globalization and human rights advocacy have begun to influence African attitudes towards homosexuality. The push for freedom of speech, recognition of human rights, and the prevalence of Western ideas have led to increased visibility and openness around homosexuality and related issues. This shift has allowed some individuals within African societies to openly identify as homosexuals among related sexual orientations and advocate for their rights.

Whereas media has been a catalyst of homosexual introduction to African, some European and American organizations have taken deliberate steps in the promotion of their uptake in the

continent (Nyeck & Epprecht, 2013). Global human rights organizations have emphasized the importance of inclusivity and non-discrimination based on sexual orientation. These ideas, introduced from outside Africa, have spurred conversations about LGBTQ+ rights and acceptance within local communities. As African societies among them Christians and other religions, continue to grapple with the tension between traditional values and global human rights standards, the discourse on homosexuality becomes even more complex.

The conversation regarding homosexuality and related issues among Christians in Africa ought to take into consideration not only the global context but also how the Bible is used to respond to the challenge in the African context. It is noteworthy that the utilization of the Bible becomes imperative when addressing all ethical matters within the Christian tradition for it is relevant and has binding authority among Christians today (Wells, 2017, p.6). It is recognized that bridging ethics and biblical teachings necessitates interpretation and contextual adaptation. A considerable challenge arises when applying the teachings of the New Testament (NT) to address ethical concerns due to the historical and cultural chasms separating the modern reader from the original authors and recipients. Scholars of interpretation of the Bible have made some effort to explain the implications of these chasms in seeking to get meaning of the ancient biblical texts in the present 21st diverse contexts (Kyomya, 2010).

The present challenge revolves around the reconciliation of NT teachings, originating in the first century, with the complexities of the present era especially the African context. The question frequently posed touches on how to effectively bridge the gaps between NT teachings and contemporary realities. Due to the many perplexing ethical issues confronting Christians today, the call for guidance from the Bible becomes critical. In light of this, this paper undertakes an examination of some existing paradigms and approaches for interpreting the NT particularly on matters of ethics within the present day African context. The African situation though variegated in beliefs and practices, is nevertheless united based on the identical persistent traditional African worldview. Focusing on the entire Bible cannot be handled in such a brief paper. Other religions of the world have their own views on ethics which may or may not be similar to those of Christianity, but it is beyond the scope of this paper.

Methodology

This study examined existing literature drawing from their insights on ethics in general and specifically on homosexuality. The focus is to provide comprehensive explanation into the ethical framework within the NT and its applicability in the contemporary African context. The methodology encompasses the following:

1. Discussion of NT Ethics

The initial step involved hermeneutical examination of the ethical principles inherent in the NT, with a specific focus on the teachings of Jesus and Paul who are the main teachers of ethics in the NT. This examination aimed to expound the foundational ethical tenets as articulated in the NT.

2. Evaluation of Existing Ethical Models

Subsequent to the explanation of NT ethics, the study proceeds to examine models advanced by scholars especially their adherence to basic biblical interpretation such as faithfulness to its original context. The principles of exegesis seek to understand a text within its original context before applying it to the present situations. The main reason is to determine the relevance of the particular ethical teaching and viability within our current diverse situations.

3. Assessment of Challenges

The assessment of the challenges encountered by Christians when employing the NT as a guide for ethical decision-making is done. By identifying these challenges, the study seeks to provide a holistic perspective on the practical difficulties faced by individuals striving to integrate NT teachings into contemporary ethical choices.

4. Hermeneutical Approach

Recognizing the necessity for a sound hermeneutical approach to comprehend the NT's meaning, the methodology emphasizes the adoption of a relevant methodology. Mburu (2019) acknowledges the importance of proper interpretation of the Bible as well as understanding the African context.

Given the cultural diversity and distinctive contextual aspects of the African situation, the methodology highlights the importance of reading the text in its originating context and understanding the African situation informed by traditional worldview. This contextualized approach allows interpreters situated in specific African contexts to derive meaning from the text through a culturally informed conceptual framework and procedure.

By using contextual hermeneutics, the study seeks to examine NT ethics, their relevance in the contemporary sphere, and the challenges faced in their application. This systematic methodology serves as a reliable guide to address the question of ethics as it relates to homosexuality and at the same time contribute to the ongoing discourse on ethical decision-making rooted in the NT.

The methodology sought first to assess the ethical models from the NT perspective. In the second place explore how it plays out in the African context is explored. The first concern is a discussion on ethics and ethical views in the NT.

Ethics in the New Testament

The NT is both the crown and in some ways an interpretation of the Old Testament (OT). Jesus severally referred to the OT in his instructions to his disciples indicating that he was rendering the OT relevant. The Sermon on the Mount in Matthew 5-7 captured, among other matters, direct ethical teachings of Jesus. In Matthew 5:17, he stated, “Do not think that I came to destroy the Law or the prophets. I did not come to destroy but to fulfill.”

The ethics of Paul is basically based on the teachings of Jesus. It is noteworthy that it was Paul and not Jesus who explicitly addressed the subject of homosexuality. The details of his ethical focus is discussed later in the paper.

Before examining how the NT addresses the issue of homosexuality, the paper looks at the various models of NT ethics propounded by scholars. The first reason is to show diversity of approaches. Secondly, is to establish the strengths and the weaknesses of each model indicating the extend of relevance.

Ethical Models and Applying New Testament Teachings Today

Scholars in their endeavor to present the ethical relevance of the NT for contemporary ethical decision-making situations have come up with a variety of perspectives. This diversity has given rise to a range of ethical models resulting in continued deliberations about the most effective methodologies. The matter of how to ground ethical decisions in the NT, particularly within the context of Christian faith especially in Africa, will remain a matter for further scholarly inquiry. Hartin (1987, 1991) has identified some ethical models related to the NT encompassing an ‘ethics of laws’ approach, an ‘ethics of ‘principles’ framework, an ‘ethics of ideals’ paradigm, and an ‘encounter with God’ model or relationality-response ethics. This paper focuses on critical engagement of these models, assessing their applicability and implication for today.

1. An Ethics of Laws Model

According to the proponents of this model, what the NT says is to be taken literally and applied without any alteration in today’s context. They argue that the NT comprises laws requiring direct obedience. According to Longenecker (1984, p. 2), God has given laws in both the OT and NT in form of commandments and ordinances, which must be adhered to. Divine command theory lines with this perspective, arguing that an action is wrong simply because God has forbidden it (Wilkens, 2017, p. 125).

In supporting this position, Dodd (1975) reiterates that every detail of the various laws contained in the NT are imperative and Christians must obey them. However, Dodd draws a distinction between codes and precepts. Codes are supposed to give detailed attention to every specific situation that may arise but precepts give general direction to individual actions (Curran, 1984, p. 181).

Some sections of the NT appear to support the ethics of laws model because they are stated in a seemingly prescriptive manner. The table below brings it out some examples of how Jesus referenced the OT.

Subject	NT	OT
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Jesus us of OT law	Mark 12:29-30	Deuteronomy 6:45
Loving neighbor	Mark 12:31	Leviticus 19:18
Honoring parents	Mark 7:10; Matthew 15:4	Exodus 20:12;21:17
Permanence of Marriage	Mark 10:7-8; Mat. 19:5	Genesis 2:24

Some scholars argue that Matthew presents Jesus as the new Lawgiver reflected in the sermon on the mount in Matthew 5 – 7 (Sietman, 2019; Bockmuehl, 2022). Johns Gospel portrays Jesus’ teachings as commandments requiring obedience (John 13:34; 14:15; 14:21; 15:10,12), the leading one is love as the ‘New Commandment’ (Chang, 2014). Guthrie (1981 p.894) notes that Jesus bases His authority on the OT as well as on His own person in giving commandments. Paul and Peter in their writings paint Christianity as giving a new ‘commandment’ (1 Tim. 6:14; 2 Peter 2:21).

The shortfalls of this model are twofold. First, it fails to take into consideration the need to first understand the Scriptures in its original context (Hamadi, 2022). Biblical exegesis demands that before one can understand the text in the present, one must understand it in its original context (Fee, 2000, p. 19). Without knowing what the text meant, what it means will likely be missed (Yilbet, 2000). In Nel’s (2018) words:

The textual and revelatory meaning of biblical texts adheres to contexts—that is, the original contexts—and the fusion of the contexts of historical and contemporary interpreters are then productive of interpretations whose meanings are accountable to the original texts themselves, which are properly understood only in relation to these original contexts. In this way, the interpreter is accountable to the texts origination (p. 11).

Appropriate interpretation is required to move from the original to the present context. Secondly, the Bible is not first a law book but rather a message of salvation. It is noteworthy that though the Bible contains laws of diverse kinds, which relate to God and those relating to social life, its main concern is on relationship between God and humanity. The first five books of the Bible are called the Torah meaning ‘the Law’ (Greengus, 2019). Apart from about 613 laws in the OT, other types

literature found there and in the NT include, narratives, prophecy, songs, gospels, epistles, and apocalyptic writings.

The Bible as a whole reveals the good news of the liberation of humanity from evil and all forces of enslavement either spiritual, physical or social. There is a call to all to respond to the message of salvation instead of looking at it only as a book containing laws that demand obedience. If the NT is treated as law book it misses out one important point, that of transformation of hearts and lives of humans. To Longenecker treating the Bible simply as a law would lack transformative power but merely inhibits non-moral behavior. Another similar thought is deontology that treats ethics in terms of duties and obligations.

One objective of this approach is bridging the difficulties caused by cultural differences between the first century and the present. Prevailing philosophical and cultural thoughts are powerful forces that have majorly influenced church theological positions on many matters including sexuality.

This model is irrelevant for the African Christian for it fails to take into consideration the need for proper interpretation of scripture, the inherent nature of human life, plus the traditional African understanding of the holistic nature of reality. Ethical thought forms in the African mindset are discussed elsewhere in this paper.

2. Principles Model

Another way of using the NT in ethical decisions is to see it as containing timeless principles with universal appeal. The central thought of this model is that general principles are derived from the words, laws, teachings and narratives found in both OT and the NT (Rabens, Grey, & Kovalishyn, 2021). Two main examples of universal ethical principles drawn from the NT are love and justice (Hays, 1996, p. 190). Jesus' golden rule found in Matthew 7:12 is another NT teaching that contains a universally applicable principle. The gospel writers recorded narratives and teachings of Jesus in parables and other ways that transcend direct commands but contain principles pertinent to similar or related situations today.

Longenecker has observed that Jesus' message could be summed up under three headings: "(1) the kingdom of God and its coming; (2) God the Father and the infinite value of the human soul; and (3) the higher righteousness and the commandment of love" (1984, p.4). If the Sermon on the Mount is interpreted as providing a summary of moral principles and not merely the laying down of rules and regulations for one's conduct, then they can be applied to all cultures in all contexts.

The strength of this model is its flexibility and the universality of applying NT teachings in diverse contemporary situations. This applies to both personal morality as well as social morality. While the biblical laws and precepts may not directly be universally applied, principles drawn from them remain unchanged because they are universal in nature. The duty of the interpreter is to examine beneath the rules and regulations relating to particular ethical issues in order to uncover the universal principles, which could have elicited legislation. Such principles can now be applied to the ethical issues of the present day contexts.

However, shortfalls exist regarding this model especially because it depends on the skill and sensitivity of specific interpreters making it difficult for its usability for the ordinary NT reader. Moreover, ethics must go beyond just rules and regulations to encompass its starting point as relationship with God resulting in inner transformation leading to outward ethical conduct. Evangelicalism majorly insists that ethics are dependent on biblical theological considerations of both the OT and NT (Blocher, 2015). Pettegrew (2000) contends that proper knowledge of ethics must be grounded in systematic theology.

3. An Ethics of Ideals Model

This ethical model presents a framework through which decisions are made on the basis of ideals drawn from the NT. Rather than treating the laws found in the NT and the rest of the Bible as obligatory on the Christian they should be regarded providing the direction towards which the believer's life is to follow. This is similar to teleological approach in ethics which is goal oriented. Ethical actions should not be measured by what is attained or achieved but judged according to the goal or the intention guiding the action.

One of the strengths of this model is that it places Jesus' moral authority at the core of consideration in ethical issues. It is however doubtful that the NT message can be summed up into a neat law of ideals. The eschatological perspective in the Bible is used to support this view (Gustafson, 1984, p.162). The model is applied majorly to the OT prophecies especially their future oriented dimension. The NT also talks of the coming of the kingdom of God partially in the present and its future full realization. It is noteworthy that scholars have argued for two-dimensional nature of eschatology encompassing the already and the not-yet (Finger, 2020; Guthrie, 1981, pp., 895-6). The existence of divergent interpretive approaches to the meaning of eschatology as presented in the NT is a drawback to this model. Ethics must be practiced now, otherwise it would defeat the purpose for which it was given in the scripture.

4. Encounter with God model

This model emphasizes the personal relation with God, which results in obedience to God and not to some abstract principle. While the individual is reading scripture God's Spirit enlightens him/her on the meaning and possibly its application. It goes against legalistic reading and application of the scripture. According to Brunner (2002, pp. 82-83) obedient behavior or obedient love in Crook's perspective (2016, p.41) based on relationship with God is the goal of conduct. This is a result of obedient submission to the free, sovereign will of God. One is to be concerned with always doing what God wills at any particular moment.

Due to its existentialist tendencies, making it subjective, this model has shortfalls. The interpretation of the scripture becomes extremely subjective. Because there is a rejection of laws and principles, Christian ethics comes under the whims of the individual. Christianity has both individualistic as well as communal aspects informed by the scripture and in some cases tradition.

5. Relationality-response model

It is also called an ethics of relations and responses model or responsibility ethics (Hartin, 1987 p. 37). The foundation of this model is that God has acted in history by providing salvation through the redemptive activity of Christ. The Christian then responds in action and faith based a living relationship.

The leading proponent was Gustafson (1965, p. 309-316) following Karl Barth's theology who stated that the understanding of the Bible does not rest in the revelation of a morality but in the revelation of a living God. In virtue ethics, actions proceed out of one's understanding of purpose of humanity which according to Kallenberg) is relation with God (2017, pp. 31-64. God's revelation action calls for a response from the Christian repentance being the first step in this response.

According to the proponents of this view, Christianity is a relationship with God and not mere keeping of rules. Christianity is more than just a religion of rules and laws but a way of life (Hector, 2023). The basis of this is a continual relationship with the person of Jesus Christ.

This model has several strengths to it. First, it bridges the historical distance between the world of the NT and the present. However, care must be taken in trying to deal with the historical question. Second, it regards NT as going beyond the question of morality. Ethics is done in the context of theology. Third, it underscores the point that the call of the NT is beyond personal change but embraces Christ's salvation work extended to others as well. Fourth, the new type of Christianity is lived in vertical and horizontal relations, it is a relationship between God and fellow humans. This has resulted from a response to God's redemptive activity through Christ.

NT Ethics and Homosexuality

The ethical framework within the NT exhibits a dynamic interplay between personal and societal dimensions. Jesus and Paul are the two main contributors of NT ethics within their broader theological, Christological, eschatological, and pneumatological teachings which set them apart from secular ethical paradigms of the time.

It is noteworthy that NT ethics in its rootedness is grounded in the ethical teachings of the OT. Contrary to the notion of starting from scratch, Jesus built his teaching on ethics on the preexisting OT principles, but enhanced by his modifications of the same. Jesus encapsulated the OT decalogue in the command to love God and neighbor (Matthew 22:37-39; Mark 12:30; Luke 10:27). Though Jesus did not explicitly address the issue of homosexuality, he implicitly responded to the matter when he gave the OT the stamp of authority and pointing out the heterosexual nature

of marriage. His endorsement of the OT implies that he sanctioned its strong prohibition of homosexual behavior. In Leviticus, it is stated:

Do not lie with a man as one lies with a woman; that is detestable. (Leviticus 18:22)

If a man lies with a man as one lies with woman, both of them have done what is detestable.

They must be put to death; their blood will be on their own heads. (Leviticus 20:13)

A majority of Biblical scholars agree that the judgment of Sodom and Gomorrah in Genesis 19: 24-25 was because of their practice of homosexuality. Ahern (2018) has given an in-depth examination of the subject by tracing historical development of the idea and interpretation of relevant texts. Some have however challenged that traditional position (Wu, 2023).

While responding to a question by the Pharisees in Matthew 19: 4-5, Jesus explained both the permanence and heterosexual character of marriage based on the authority of Genesis 1:27. He reiterated in the text, “Haven’t you read ... that at the beginning the creator made them male and female?”

A close examination of the Sermon on the Mount (Matthew 5:21ff.), shows that Jesus did not do away with OT ethical teachings but heightened it, highlighting its inner essence through the phrases ‘it was said’ and ‘But I say’. While affirming the authority of the OT, he established his own distinct authority, introducing a Christological dimension to NT ethics. The applicability of the OT ethics for today should therefore take into consideration Jesus’ endorsement. According to Goldingay (2021), “Both Testaments are resources for the community’s understanding of God’s expectations”. (p. 177).

Eschatology, first explained by Braaten (2017), forms another dimension of NT ethics. If the kingdom of God has indeed been realized, it has a positive influence on the ethical standards upheld by its members. Simultaneously, the future dimension of this ethics remains paramount, as the complete fulfillment of Jesus’ ethical teachings awaits the consummation of the kingdom. Scholars have pointed out the present and future dimensions of understanding the Kingdom as ‘the already’ and ‘the not yet’ (Willis, 2020, p. 187).

Further, some scholars have explored the relationship between NT ethics and pneumatology emphasizing the role of the Holy Spirit in empowering the recipient (Wenk, 2004, Wenk, 2022; Berkman, 2023). The indwelling Spirit empowers believers to uphold the high ethical standards taught by Jesus (Redick, 2023). This dimension underscores the intrinsic connection between Christian ethics and the communal context of the Church (ecclesiastical dimension) then and now. The ecclesiastical dimension of NT ethics intersects with the redemptive mission of Jesus through the power of the Holy Spirit.

Each Gospel writer employed a specific approach to convey ethical teachings (Shin, 2018; Stanley, 2018). Mark, for instance, employs narrative techniques, while Matthew focuses on Jesus' moral teachings in the Sermon on the Mount. Across the synoptic gospels, the concept of the Kingdom of God serves as a moral benchmark that contrasts the then prevailing world standards. In John's gospel, the emphasis shifts towards Christology.

Guthrie summarizes Paul's ethical perspective in the following words, "What appears in bud in the ethics of Jesus appears in full flower in Paul" (1981, p. 913). Paul build his ethical teachings upon Jesus' ethical foundations especially as directed towards both Jews and Gentiles now integrated into the new humanity of Christ; the church (Drane, 1986, p. 172). Empowered by the Spirit, believers are equipped to lead lives characterized by holiness and ethical integrity. Paul's approach to ethics is non-legalistic and is spirit-guided. Notably, the principle of love, which is his core ethical principle, is the central subject of 1 Corinthians 13, advanced as the primary motivation for Christian living.

The specific passages where homosexuality is mentioned are those found in Pauline epistles. One such passage is Romans 1:26-27, often cited as condemning homosexual behavior. Townsley (2013, p.3) argues that the passage, within its cultural context, actually focuses on idolatry through existence of goddess cults or even polytheism and the consequences of turning away from God. Some have even suggested queer relationship seen in the perceived presence of some form of lesbianism (Murphy, 2019). The sexual actions mentioned are seen as a result of humanity's rejection of divine authority, rather than a singular focus on ethical aspects. Malick (1993) did a

contextual and exegetical examination of Romans 1:26–27, refuting attempts to dismiss Paul's prohibitions against same-sex relations. He concludes that Paul condemned homosexuality terming it a perversion of God's design for human sexual relations based on biblical doctrine of creation.

Another set of passages is found in 1 Corinthians 6:9 and 1 Timothy 1:10, which mention "practicing homosexuals" among those who will not inherit the kingdom of God. These passages, when studied through a historical lens, shed light on practices like pederasty prevalent in their context (Schreiner, 2016). Though this historical understanding suggests that the passages may not directly address the modern concept of consensual, committed same-sex relationships, it nevertheless condemns the practice.

In essence, the ethical dimensions presented by Jesus and Paul within the NT encompass theological, Christological, eschatological, and pneumatological understanding. They collectively contribute to a comprehensive understanding of ethical principles in the context of faith and Christian life then and now.

Ethics in Traditional African Thought

Traditional African worldview informs all dimensions of African life including ethics or morality. Whereas Africans acknowledge God has the source of all morality, it is important to comprehend the complex nature of its understanding and outworking (Kunhiyop, 2008, p. 66). The traditional African worldview at its core is religious in character and is expressed in moral law according to Turaki (2019, p. 42) which can be divided into four dimensions: holism, spirituality, dynamism, and communalism.

1. Holism

Traditional African worldview sees reality as integrated meaning it is holistic in nature with no dichotomy between the sacred and the secular, the religious and the ordinary. All aspects of life must be treated as one and thus must work in harmony. In reference to ethics or morality, it finds expression in this law of harmony.

The law of harmony demands that ontological balance must be maintained at all levels of life at the personal level and community level touching the spirit world, nature and the human world. Disharmony results when an individual breaches fellowship resulting in the disturbance of ontological balance through the sins of commission or omission. An individual is guilty of these sins when he/she fails to observe prohibitions, abominations or taboos.

Because the spirits are the custodians of the moral law, they mete out punishment upon the perpetrators and even the community at large. Calamities both at individual and communal levels are indications or symptoms of displeasure of the spirit beings due to a person breaking the moral law. In order to restore harmony and mitigate the damage due to impropriety, religious specialists prescribe relevant sacrifices, offerings, and observances of taboos (Turaki, 2006, p. 44). In African understanding, an action is moral or immoral only based on its effect on cosmic harmony.

Though sin is understood at individual level, the overall biblical understanding encompasses the community leading to disruption of spiritual and natural harmony. This is more common in the OT understanding where the sins of individuals affected their families and the entire community. When Achan failed to observe what Joshua had commanded, the Israelites were defeated in their battle against Ai in Joshua chapter 7 and 8 until Achan and his family were judged by stoning.

2. Spirituality

The law of the spirit is a central thought in traditional African societies. Reality is not just natural but spiritual. Spiritual forces are the ones who control and determine every event and action in the natural world. Every event good or bad are interpreted spiritually. Spirit agencies may bring calamities upon individuals when they break prohibitions especially the taboos (Turaki, 2019).

Expediency, existentialism and pragmatism define Africans' search for meaning and not mere concern for moral action or moral behavior. Every action is directed towards the success of the individual and the community one belongs to rather than to pleasing the supreme being.

The will of the Supreme Being occupies second place to the search for spiritual meaning and the responsibility of finding spiritual answers in life. For that reason, moral action or behavior is

directed towards finding spiritual meaning, regardless of its source. Getting spiritual meaning in life determines if an action or behavior is judged bad or unacceptable.

3. Dynamism

Dynamism refers to the law of power whereby every action relating to one's destiny has to be determined by the ability to manipulate or control the supernatural powers. It is the belief in the 'life-force' that can be tapped by human beings for good or evil purposes (Anderson, 1992, p. 12). Africans seek for ability or power to overcome negative forces in life, which among others include sickness, death, poverty, misfortune, sorcery, oppression, injustice, witchcraft, evil spirits, famine, and floods. The sources of this power include ancestors, charms and magic, sacrifices, prayer, sacred objects and places, but ultimately from the Supreme Being (Ibeabuchi, 2013, p. 289). Any action or behavior is termed bad or inappropriate if it does not lead to finding spiritual or mystical powers to deal with problems in life.

4. Communalism

Communalism refers to the law of kinship defining obligations and accountability structures. Africans' central belief is that protection, meaning, identity and one's status are imbedded in kinship, which extends to include the divinities, ancestors and the soon to be born. Therefore, what defines or guides one's behavior in relation to the spirit world, family, and tribe are such terms as "loyalty, affinity and obligations" (Turaki, 2019, p. 48). The central guiding principles of morality are:

Self-interest, kinship-interest, group-interest, territorial-interest, tribal-interest or racial-interest takes precedence over all other social and ethical considerations. This self-interest is sanctioned in the interests of the kinship community. (Turaki, 2019, p. 48).

In this regard, African morality of communalism implies ethical relativism. The outsiders are excluded from benefiting from the same moral and ethical principles since the community takes precedence above all else.

It is noteworthy that the law of kinship denotes that individual's action is never isolated from the community. Any moral action either of praiseworthy or blameworthy character become shared responsibility with one's community. In some cases, the spirits connected to the particular community are regarded as the source of a person's moral actions.

Overall, traditional African understanding and practice of ethics has at its core religious explanation. As noted above the Supreme Being is the ultimate source of morality and finds expression through the law of harmony, the law of the spirit, the law of power, and the law of kinship.

African Attitudes towards Homosexuality

Homosexuality is a topic that evokes diverse reactions across cultures, and African societies have their own complex set of attitudes toward this issue. Traditional African perspectives on sexuality, communal values, and the impact of globalization have all contributed to shaping the continent's views on homosexuality.

Most African societies place a strong emphasis on communal values and family structures. Traditional African cultures tend to interpret human behavior from a communal perspective rather than focusing solely on individual preferences. The purpose of sexual relations in these cultures goes beyond mere pleasure; it is often closely linked to procreation and the well-being of the community. Magesa (2014) highlights the importance of continuing the family legacy through siring of offspring resulting from formalized marriage. Together, with impotence and barrenness, traditional African communities regard homosexuality as an abnormality (Magesa, 2014, p. 136).

Though some isolated homosexual practices have been documented in a few traditional communities informed by circumstantial factors (Epprecht, 2021), most African communities regard homosexuality as taboo and if some incidences emerge they are treated with distaste. Homosexuality generally goes contrary to their beliefs and values. It is discussed in hushed tones in case of occurrences. Traditionally, sexual norms are guided by traditional customs and religious beliefs, based on the idea that sexual activity is majorly for procreation and should contribute to the continuation of the community and the family.

African ethics, in particular attitudes toward homosexuality are influenced by traditional African religious and cultural factors (Gbadegesin, 2022). Most African societies have strong emphasis on religious traditions that condemn homosexual behavior. Just like in all other dimensions of Christianity and Islam, Africans are influenced by their traditional religions in their beliefs and practices revolving around sexuality and sexual ethics (Kunhiyop, 2008, p.15).

However, the role of religion in shaping attitudes toward homosexuality is not uniform across the continent. Some religious leaders and institutions in Africa are calling for a greater acceptance and inclusion of LGBTQ+ individuals (Van Klinken, Bompani, & Parsitau, 2023). This highlights the diversity of thought within African religious communities and the ongoing dialogue around sexual ethics.

Ethical Decision-making within the Context of Christian Faith in Africa

The foregone discussion as revealed diversity in understanding ethics envisaged in the NT. Furthermore, it is noted that the Traditional African Worldview informs ethics in the African setup. An individual Christian's decision-making doesn't occur in isolation but within the context of the larger Christian community. The NT documents emerged from the milieu of the early Christian community. The message to make sense to them had to be framed using their thought forms informed by their worldview. Daly's insight underscores this interconnectedness:

What the biblical author wrote arose from the community. So also, the reader must be aware of the community as a source of interpretation and as recipient of communication from the reader (Daly, 1984, p. 294).

However, the community's endorsement doesn't automatically validate an action. Rightness or wrongness isn't determined by a majority vote. The bedrock for Christians lies in the authority of the Bible, appropriately interpreted. While community support is valuable, ultimate ethical judgment is rooted in faithful biblical interpretation, thus preserving the integrity of Christian principles.

Homosexuality and the African Christian

As already intimated, homosexuality is a complex and contentious topic, with a range of perspectives shaping the discourse. Scholars and advocates have categorized homosexuality into pervers and inverts as distinct groups reflecting the diverse attitudes towards the practice (Weeks, 2014).

Perverts, as defined, are individuals who, despite being primarily heterosexual, occasionally engage in homosexual acts. Their actions might reflect a deviation from their true sexual orientation. This category introduces intriguing ethical questions, as it delves into the decision-making processes of individuals whose actions may conflict with their inherent inclinations.

On the other hand, inverts represent individuals who are genuinely homosexual. Their sexual attraction aligns with their inherent nature. For these individuals, ethical discussions might hold less relevance, as their attractions and behaviors are in harmony with their fundamental identity. This perspective raises questions about the role of ethics in addressing innate characteristics and whether the same ethical framework should be applied universally across diverse sexual orientations.

Scholars argue that while pervers might engage in a moral dialogue surrounding their choices, inverts present a challenge to traditional ethical frameworks because according to their orientation they are homosexual. There is a recommendation that ethical judgments cannot be uniformly used across individuals with distinct sexual orientations.

In trying to respond to modern challenges in addressing homosexuality from a biblical perspective, it is pertinent to appreciate that interpretations of relevant biblical passages are influenced by broader theological beliefs. Daly (1984) notes that the community's beliefs shape individual interpretations, highlighting the communal dimension of understanding scripture. Jesus and Paul, as already noted, disapproved homosexuality highlighting God's original intention in creation. Therefore, the African Christians though informed by traditional perspective are nevertheless ultimately guided by the teachings of the NT.

Conclusion and Recommendation

Drawing from the teachings of Jesus and Paul in the NT, it is noted that homosexuality is unacceptable from the biblical perspective. The evaluation of the existing models on NT ethics brought out strengths and weaknesses of each with implications for the African Christian. The discussion has revealed that the Bible when appropriately interpreted with the consideration of the contexts established that both Jesus and Paul disapprove homosexual relationship. Furthermore, it is noted that the majority of African communities base their ethics on the laws of harmony, spirit, power, and kinship. Many treat homosexuality with distaste. The paper concludes by underscoring the importance of understanding diverse perspectives and employing relevant hermeneutical approaches in addressing ethical concerns within the African context. While acknowledging the challenges of reconciling scripture with traditional African cultural understanding, it proposes the need for continued thoughtful dialogue touching on the relevant ethical challenges. The paper recommends the development of contextualized theological resources and pastoral practices that are sensitive to the realities and experiences related to homosexuality and other ethical challenges in Africa.

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